

Pragma-stylistic Analysis of “Moth Smoke”

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Abstract

The investigation may concentrate on the following topics: the century and region, how things transpired, hot-button problems and conflicts, character development, and symbolism for a thorough analysis of the novel. The purposes of the study are achieved through the use of qualitative research. This study is based on the levels of formalist perspectives, such as the setting, plot, theme, character development, and the use of language in the novel. The research methodology, population and sample, conversation, or dialogues to be analyzed, research design, instrument, data collection, data analysis. This study deals with the pragma-stylistic analysis of the novel *Moth Smoke* by Mohsin Hamid. In this research qualitative approach is used to analyze the text with descriptive analysis of the dialogues. With the help of pragma-stylistics analysis this novel is analyzed. The present study has adopted qualitative paradigms. The text of Hamid’s novel, *Moth Smoke* has been selected as the data. For the purpose of data analysis, a systematic procedure is used. Firstly, the researcher took a close reading of the novel to keenly observe the characters and the choice of words of different characters. Close reading gives an insight to the researcher how the characters are built and the gradual development of the novel. *Moth Smoke* is one of the most famous novels of Mohsin Hamid. Mohsin Hamid is Pakistani writer who spent most of his time out of Pakistan. He used to write the fundamental issues of Pakistan in all his piece of writings. “*The Moth Smoke*” is his first novel which was globally acknowledged.

Keywords: moth smoke, qualitative approach, pragma-stylistics analysis

1. Introduction

The study that will be used to do the essential research for the investigation is briefly described in this chapter. The study aims: to investigate the time and geographic location, investigate how events and occasions happened, to investigate burning issues and conflicts, to investigate the character delineation and to investigate the symbolism for the in-depth study of the novel. Qualitative research is adopted to achieve the objectives of the study.

1.1. Background of the Study

This Article aimed to describe the pragma-stylistic analysis of *Moth smoke* written by Mohsin Hamid. This is one of his best-selling novels, which earns him a lot of fame. Writing can take in many different forms and styles; the major focus of this research is to find out figures of speech through Pragma stylistic analysis of Mohsin Hamid's novel & *Moth Smoke*. Quote; a book is a work of fictional based on the author's imagination.

1.2. Stylistics

Stylistics is the study of linguistic items (such as dramatic figures and syntactical patterns) that are supposed to generate expressive or literary styles.

Since ancient times, the style has been a topic of study. The style was seen as the proper ornamentation of the mind by Aristotle, Cicero, Demetrius, and Quintilian. Style devices can be cataloged in this perspective, which were prevalent during the Renaissance period.

Mood: The mood of a work, the narrator's attitude

The speed with which the story unfolds is referred to as pacing.

The narrator's point of view; first person (I) or third person (T) (he or she)

Symbolism is the use of a tale element to signify something else.

Theme: The major theme or big concept of work; the message communicated by or shown in it.

Tone refers to the writer's attitude toward the subject or the way he or she chooses terminology and presents information, for example, informal or formal.

Line-by-Line Elements

Alliteration is the use of a close repeat of consonants for effect.

Assonance: The use of close vowel repetition for effect.

Colloquialisms: Slang and regional terminology are examples of informal words.

Diction: The fundamental clarity of the grammar or how the characters talk, such as with an accent or by using poor grammar.

Jargon is a term that refers to terms that are specialized in a particular field.

Repetition: Using the same words or phrases repeatedly in a short period to emphasize a point.

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When the same sounds emerge in two or more words, it's called rhyming.

Rhythm: The use of stressed and unstressed syllables in poetry sections, in addition to modified or repeating phrases in paragraphs, to give writing a musical quality.

A stylistic is someone who studies one or more of the following overlapping sub disciplines of stylistics:

1.3. Styles of writing

Forms such as poetry, theatre, and prose are studied. Interpretive stylistics is the study of how linguistic factors interact to produce meaningful art.

Evaluative stylistics is the study of how an author's style works—or doesn't work—in a piece of writing.

Discourse stylistics: How the language in usage creates meaning, such as examining parallelism, assonance, alliteration, and rhyme.

The study of what happens in the mind when it comes into contact with the language is known as cognitive stylistics.

1.4. Mohsin Hamid as Stylistics Writer

Hamid was born in Lahore in 1970 and is a well-known author, lawyer, and journalist. He lived in the United States for part of his boyhood. His father, a university professor, was obtaining a Ph.D. at Stanford University at the time. He and his family afterwards relocated to Lahore, Pakistan, where he was accepted into the Lahore American School. He returned to the United States in 1993. He received his bachelor's degree from Princeton University and had the opportunity to study famous authors such as Joyce, Carol Oates, and Toni Morrison (Anderson, 2010; Hamid, 2012).

He didn't spend any more time and finished *Moth Smoke*. In 2006, he became a dual citizen of the United Kingdom and the United States. He also continued to visit Pakistan, and in 2009, he and his family relocated to Lahore. He split his time between Pakistan and other countries. He continued to go to places like Lahore, New York, London, and the Mediterranean. Hamid also got the opportunity to travel to Italy and Greece.

He's published several essays, short stories, articles, and three novels to date: *Moth Smoke* (2000), *The Reluctant Fundamentalist* (2007), and *How to Get Filthy Rich in Rising Asia* (2013).

1.5. Styles in *Moth Smoke*

Hamid's debut novel, *Moth Smoke* (MS), is divided into nine parts, 17 chapters, and 246 pages. There's also a prologue and an epilogue. When it was initially released in 2000, it moved up to cult classic status in the Indo-Pak area... Experts praised it, and it won significant accolades such as the Pulitzer Prize for Fiction, the New York Times Notable Book of the Year 2000, the 2001 Betty Trask Award, and the 2001 Hemingway Foundation / Pen Award. It was also made into a Pakistani television series. GEO, a Pakistani television station, broadcasted a film called "Daira."

He also collaborates with Murad Bad shah on a heist scheme to loot a store, but unfortunately, he murders a little kid in the process. Finally, Ozi exacts vengeance on him by having him jailed for the crime of crushing a youngster, which he committed using his money and crooked system. The novel has a lot of ramifications. It serves as an analogy for the current condition of events in Pakistan. It "exposes socioeconomic disparities in Pakistani urban life and remarks on unequal income distribution as a method of mounding the lives of people from various social strata" (Tariq, 2008, p. 107).

1.6. Statement of the Problem

The research problem of this study identifies Pragma-stylistic elements such as grammatical forms, phonological features, and proposed meanings of the text from the novel *Moth Smoke* by Mohsin Hamid.

1.7. Significance of the Research

The pragma_stylistic features of the book *Moth Smoke* are examined in this article. This study will add to prior linguistics research, notably in the areas of pragmatics and stylistics. As a result of this research, the reader's understanding of pragmatics, particularly how to use components, should increase.. This research will also serve as a foundation for future studies.

1.8. Objectives of the Study

This study is designed with the following objectives in view:

- To investigate Mohsin Hamid's dialogues to comprehend better by applying pragma stylistic analysis

2. Literature Review

This chapter provides a thorough analysis of the study's associated literature, which will be used to carry out the necessary research for the study. A review of the *Moth Smoke* literature is presented in this section.

Mohsin Hamid, a Pakistani author, wrote the novel *Moth Smoke*. The plot takes place in Lahore and centers on a man's decline in status within Pakistan's upper elite after losing his job. As he declines, he becomes addicted to drugs, has an affair with his closest friend's wife, and is jailed for murder.

In his definition of pragma stylistics, Owplabi (2010) states that it is a concept that analyses the look of a text and linguistic choices. Pragma-stylistics, he claims, comprises morphological viewpoint, pragmatics, and stylistics. Pragma stylistics is a unique synthesis of two disciplines. Pragmatic literary stylistic analysis is the application of related

pragmatic ideas to the comprehension of a literary work. Clarke (2009:5) claims that pragmatic stylistics is not a well-defined term.

2.1. Descriptive Qualitative

A descriptive qualitative technique of analysis, as well as a heuristic and hermeneutic reading approach, are used in this study. Following that, the approach is used to listen carefully and completely to the substance of the tale, and then to document all facts by formulating research topics. Occurrences, Social reality includes social processes, social difficulties, social development, and social structures.

Marginalization, subordination, stereotyping, violence, and workload are used to symbolize gender injustice in the novel, whereas access, involvement, and control are used to represent gender equality. The researcher refers to the use of concrete language styles (special, greeting, connotative, and foreign) as a type of pragmatic stylistics in this study. The current research is descriptive and analytical in nature, and it is centered on studying and comprehending the use of intensifiers utilizing Holmes (1984) and Cacchiani's models (2009). The writer, according to the statistics, overuses intensifiers to the point that the text has 280 intensifiers. 78 percent of intensifiers are undifferentiated emotions, 13.5 percent are personal emotions, and 8.5 percent are unique emotions.

This is what I inferred from the title, and this is probably what Mohsin had in mind when he failed horribly to deliver! Despite the fact that he seemed determined to paint the narrative in all hues of heated passions and snatched jerky moments of two so-called "moths" with no fire to circle around but simply a collapse-by-coincidence,

Mumtaz, a slut of a woman with such a shallow and undeveloped character, is Mohsin's most irritating creature; I literally snarled at her uncertain state of mind and how she betrays the loving father of her very young children.

Betrayal is a sin that cannot be forgiven or forgotten!

Her adulterous liaison with her husband's closest friend demonstrates her character's wantonness and adultery, and Daru Shezad, her inveterate companion, is yet another melodramatic failure. Face upkeep is a contagious sickness in major cities, and you might feel like you're surrounded by money machines and cultured animals, talking big, bragging big, and boasting bigger.

Daru is a drug dealer and banker who end himself in prison for the death of a youngster he did not murder. There were some allusions from the period of Pakistan's initial bomb testing, as well as a lot more about aristocratic parties and drinking, and Mumtaz has to wait till he gets out.

At the same time, *Moth Smoke* was a wonderful and depressing read. It relates the narrative of a guy named Darashikoh (mercifully abbreviated to Daru) and the final debilitation he experiences as a result of his life choices. It also informs us about Mumtaz, his love, and her husband, Aurangzeb, Daru's best friend.

2.2. Moth Smoke

Moth Smoke, like most fictional plays, was driven by its people rather than the plot. We'll start with Daru and his status in the world. The action takes place in Lahore, one of Pakistan's "three big" (the other two being Islamabad and the dreaded port city of Karachi). I'm not going to go into detail about the tale because there's not much I can say in either direction.

The story is more of a monologue from Daru, who explains the whirlpool of emotions churning inside him with each step he makes toward annihilation. He was a fascinating and intelligent figure, but he was far from appealing. From the beginning to the finish, I despised Daru. However, every action taken by the man was motivated by a need that the reader gradually learns about throughout the narrative.

Mumtaz was, without a doubt, my favorite character. This lady embodies all a lady should and should not be at the same time. "I'm fascinated by the things that women do that aren't talked about."

Mumtaz's back-story was both disturbing and fascinating to read. Many women will have difficulty empathizing with her. She'd been a victim of self-doubt her whole life, a self-proclaimed monster at every turn.

While Aurangzeb plays an important part in the back stories of the characters mentioned above, he does not play a large role in the storyline. He is, nevertheless, more normalized than the rest of the group.

The novel frequently breached the fourth wall to directly address the readers, jumping between the perspectives of several main and small characters, who help the storytelling flow more smoothly by speaking their side of the Daru story. *Moth Smoke* is, after all, a love story that parallels the demise of a once-respected middle-class family man. The novel moved me, though in the end my heart sank. It is also well written, always reminding me that our writing can be compared to today's Western dramas, which often cause bleeding.

From my point of view, Mohsin Hamid has become a rock star, and I can't wait to eat *The Reluctant Fundamentalist*. "And I come with the last year, the last circle." And there he is, his eyes shining with chemical wonder." According to Anum Sultan, the aggravation I felt while reading *Moth Smoke* was similar to the frustration you get when you're watching a horror movie and the foolish side character walks towards sounds in a dark home, knowing they're about to die a horrible end

According to Zarish Fatima, the novel is about a man who wants more than he has, is ungrateful for what he has and is not ready to face the bitter reality of his existence, choosing drugs instead. The woman who does should not be. And the company that can't pay. He belongs to the middle class, but he has got a taste of the upper-class lifestyle, and it seems that he cannot overcome the fact that he is not one of them. You want what you lack, and like most, you feel you deserve it more because you are smart and think you are a better person.

Daru loses his job at the worst possible time, when the economy is in freefall and finding work is nearly difficult.

Aurangzeb - known to his pals as Ozi - has just returned from New York with his wife and child. Ozi hails from a wealthy and prominent family, with a father who is a retired government official.

Daru falls for Ozi's wife, Mumtaz, and things quickly spiral out of control. To make matters worse, he begins to experiment with heroin, a little at a time, and soon finds himself on a one-way trip down the slippery slope.

Daru mostly speaks for the story. And the reader soon becomes accustomed to its sound. Each character has their own voice. Murad has a distinctive taste of sardonic and polite Urdu in the king's soft-spoken style.

Then there's Mumtaz, who is both clear-eyed and brave. Willing to say what is on my mind.

Her emotion (or lack thereof) for her child piqued my interest. I was intrigued by the idea that Hamid had given her this aspect as well, which is one of the many reasons I enjoy this book. It looks at the notions that the maternity culture unwittingly imposes on women, making some (like Mumtaz) feel like social outcasts when they don't fit in.

Mumtaz's journey through the inevitable stages of denial and lying to herself about how she feels, and finally, acceptance of her as she is captivated me. She considers herself a monster and bemoans the fact that she doesn't feel the way she should love her son. But, in the end, she comes to terms with herself. The way her personality was painted astounded me, as did how uncannily I was able to identify to and empathize with her.

Then comes Ozi's voice, which contradicts the story of the drug, to which you have become accustomed. When Ozzy concludes by telling his childhood story, it becomes so contradictory to Daru's story that you begin to doubt both stories, and begin to doubt that the truth is in between. But you know that Daru was not lying when he said that Ozi ran over the boy. Ozzy, the master manipulator that he is, never says anything about it.

Daru, high on heroin, theories that Muazzam, Mumtaz's kid, is the source of his unhappiness somewhere in the middle. He even follows Muazzam's automobile, gun in hand, as though this is the crime for which he is being prosecuted. Only to be amazed when the infant is not killed.

Then comes the burglary scheme. You're certain Daru and Murad killed the small kid in the store they're raiding now. Even after the program ends, you're certain that this is what happened.

The major focus of the documentary is on the social and political concerns that plagued our country during the time of the nuclear testing. However, I believe that much of what is happening in Pakistan is still represented in this book: corruption, unemployment, nepotism, class division, and all of the problems that result from these. Do you want to know how Pakistan is doing these days? Read *Moth Smoke* if you haven't already. This book was about the hard realities of Pakistan's challenges.

Darashikoh Shezad, our infamous protagonist, is next. It was unjust that he had to spend the rest of his life in prison for what Ozi had done. He didn't kill the youngster in the shop, which is also true. He was not, however, blameless. He had an affair with the wife of his best buddy. He intended to assassinate his closest friend's son. He was a narcotics trafficker. I became addicted to heroin and was a miserable loser.

Ozi was a pampered youngster who believed he was the finest and that he could do whatever he wanted since his father was wealthy. As a result, I'm not going to waste my time on him.

Mumtaz was, without a doubt, my favorite character. She was strong-willed and self-reliant. She appeared to be the only one with her head held straight.

The book opens and concludes with portions from the account of Emperor Shah Jahan, who built the Taj Mahal for his lovely and loving wife, Mumtaz, according to Louise. Darashukoh and Aurangzeb, their offspring, became adversaries. Mohsin Hamid gives these historical figures names and depicts a comparable breakdown of childhood bonds in his characters.

3. Research Methodology

This study deals with the pragma-stylistic analysis of the novel *Moth Smoke* by Mohsin Hamid. In this research qualitative approach is used to analyze the text with descriptive analysis of the dialogues.

3.1. Speech acts Theory

Austin's pupil, John R. Searle (1969, 1976, and 1979) describes this theory. Searle's work on speech act theory considers one of the best contributions to the theory. The major influence of speech act theory traced back to his work. Searle's concept is based on the idea that when someone speaks a language, they are engaging in a rule-governed behavior such as asking questions, making claims, issuing demands, promising, and so on.

3.2. Grice's Cooperative Principle

The Cooperative Notion can be defined as the fundamental principle that participants in a conversation should work together and manage turn taking while speech for effective communication (Riemer, 2010, p. 119). Grice principle contributes in conversation as much is required. It helps in to manage direction and purpose of the conversation. There are four cooperative principles or maxims:

1. Quantity

Only contribute to the conversation as much information as is required.

2. Equality

Only speak what you think is true and you having enough evidence.

3. Relation

Stick to the topic, do not talk irrelevant.

4. Manner

Avoid unknown expressions, and be concise.

(Grice, 1975, cited in Leech, 1983, p. 8)

3.3. Implicature

Most writers need a maxim or a set of maxims since aesthetic compositions are not self-contained. The requirement to be useful, accurate, or relevant is self-evident. For instance, the author could make use of the principle of style, i.e., the use of ambiguous or flowery descriptions as creative means precisely the same stuff. This is especially true with lyrical ambiguity, which is supposed to be intentional (Mitchell, 2008: 65).

3.4. Model of Research

In this study of the novel *Moth smoke*, an eclectic model is used for the purpose of analysis throughout the selected data. The model is intended to describe the intensions mentioned in previous sections. Through this model, the novel is analyzed using pragma-stylistic approach.

3.5. Procedure of Data Collection

In this research, the researcher has gone through extensive number of related articles and literature that applied pragmatic and stylistic theories in the analysis of text.

4. Analysis of Data

For the purpose of data analysis, a systematic procedure is used. Firstly, the researcher took a close reading of the novel to keenly observe the choice of words of different characters.

4.1. Pragma-stylistics Analysis of Text 1 Ch#2

A steady stream of commoners and nobles follows their diversity the work of a skilled casting director. They take their places with a silent murmur, moving slowly, every hesitation well-rehearsed. A brief but stylish crowd scene, and above it all you preside like the marble rider of some great equestrian statue.

Then a pause, a silence. All eyes turn to the door.

He enters. The accused: Darashikoh Shezad.

A hard man with shadowed eyes, manacled, cuffed, disheveled, proud, erect. A man capable of anything and afraid of nothing

Two guards accompany him, and yes, they are brutes, but they would offer scant reassurance if this man were not chained.

He is the terrible almost-hero of a great story: powerful, tragic, and dangerous. He alone meets your eyes.

And then he is seated and it begins.

Your gavel falls like the hammer of God.

4.2. Foreshadow

This is a figure of speech used to describe the things which will happen later. This creates a scenario which tells the reader what situation is going to happen next. As in the above text the situation, choice of words represent that a case is going to appear in front of the court. A person is taken to the courtroom, which is considered as accused. The described situation indicates the upcoming situation that will happen later.

4.3. Repetition

In stylistic analysis repetition represents the repletion of sounds and words. The repetition of vowel and consonant sounds known as assonance and consonance. In the analysis of the text, it reveals that there is repetition of certain sounds.

4.4. Speech Acts Theory

The very first sentence of the text expresses the speech act though "stream of commoners and nobles follows. In the next line there are many words which are the representation of speech act expressions "take their place", "silent murmur", "moving slowly", "hesitation" "marble rider", "pause, silence, eyes turn". The sentence a man capable of

anything and afraid of nothing, is an expression of speech act which shows that the character about which the story is being is a person who have the power to do all the things and but still he does not do any harm to anyone. Another phrase “if this man were not chained expresses the act of being prisoner. In the text “he alone meets your eyes, is a speech act, which represent an action of looking through verbal speech. “Your gavel falls” this phrase shows the action performed through speech.

4.5. Grice’s Cooperative Principle

In the explanation of the scene of court room, the complete description of the scenario is presented in a way, A steady stream of commoners and nobles follows, take their places”, these phrases express the maxim of relevance, the words use to explain the scenario are related to the situation. The author explains the situation with required words, which represent the maxim of quantity.

4.6. Implicature

Implicature shows the intended meaning, reader grasp from the text. In the selected text “the work of skilled casting director is using”, here this phrase does not mean the director of an actual visualized play. He is explaining that the audience is well organized, they come into the room and sit according to their arrangement like someone is giving them directions to do that, but they are doing it without any specified command. Here “stylish crowd” phrase is used which represent a crowd but it shows that the crowd is not scattered instead that is well organized. Some qualities of Darashikoh are given in the text like as, “powerful, tragic, and dangerous.

4.7. Pragma -stylistics Analysis of Text 2 Ch#3

Access obtained; I cruise down a driveway too short to serve as a landing strip for a getaway plane, perhaps, and pass not one but two lovely new Pajeros. Yes, God has been kind to Ozi’s dad; the frequently investigated but as yet unincarcerated Federal Secretary (Retired) Khurram Shah. The front door opens and a servant leads me inside and upstairs. Time has ripened Ozi’s face and peeled his hairline back from his temples with two smooth strokes of a fruit knife. We crouch, facing each other with our arms spread wide, and pause for a moment, grinning. Then we embrace and he lifts me off my feet.

‘You’ve gone bald,’ I exclaim.

‘Thanks a lot, yaar,’ he replies.

Mumtaz steps forward and kisses me on the cheek. ‘Hello,

Daru,’ she says. Hoarse voice, from intimacy’s border with asthma: parched beaches, dust whipped by the wind.

4.8. Foreshadow

The first sentence “After getting access, I drive down a road that may be too short to qualify as an escape plane’s landing strip and pass not one, but two fabulous new Pajeros, This texts foreshadow a meeting between two people. The use of phrase new pajeros, indicates that the person is rich. Before this when he come to the Ozi’s house, guards at door asked him whom he wants to meet, at that time he only tells his name which shows the person whom he is going to meet is well aware of him.

4.9. Repetition

In the above text there is no repetition of any word occur. In the phrase “smooth stroke” initial consonant sound “s” is repeated. Here a phrase “me off my feet” shows the repetition of a consonant sound “m”. The phrase “she says, represent the repetition of consonant sound “s” at the initial place of both words.

4.10. Speech Acts Theory

In the initial sentence of the above text a phrase “access obtained” is an example of speech act. “I cruise down a driveway” is another example of speech act. The speaker is performing an action and expressing through words. A servant leads me inside” shows the speech act performed by the servant.

4.11. Grice’s Cooperative Principle and Use of Implicature

All the characters in the novel represent that, they have uttered only required words and their talks were stick to the topic being discussed among them. The example of quality is expressed through the following sentences. With two smooth strokes of a fruit knife; time has ripened Ozi’s face and peeled his hairline back towards his temples.”

The quantity of their conversation represented through the attractive phrases, we embrace, neither of us says hello”. Both of the friends meet they do not utter a word at first glance, they look at each other and expresses’ their feelings through their action of embracing each other.

Implicative represents that the words which are using, aims to give some other meaning which are not apparent. When Daru enters to the house of Ozi, he said that, “pass not one but two lovelies new Pajeros” in this phrase he is not telling about the vehicle they have but he is expressing the power and wealth of Ozi. “In the sentence when Daru said that, God has been kind to Ozi’s dad, he does not mean that God is kind, its implied meaning is that Ozi’s father has a lot of money which he has earned from his job in army, now he is a retired officer with a lot of wealth. In the sentence, I thump him on the back and squeeze the wind out of his lungs for good measure” shows his feelings of love and warmth for Ozi.

5. Conclusion

Moth Smoke is one of the most famous novels of Mohsin Hamid. Mohsin Hamid is Pakistani writer who spent most of his time out of Pakistan. He used to write the fundamental issues of Pakistan in all his piece of writings. The Moth Smoke is his first novel which was globally acknowledged.

The purpose of foreshadow is to indicate the reader what will be happen in the next scene of the novel or other literary text. Repetition helps to explore what is important and emphasized within the text. Speech act theory helps to understand the intention of the speaker and what it affects of the listener or reader. This theory applied on this text to interpret what the writer intended to convey, how the characters interact with each other and what kind of impacts this conversation leave on the reader.

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